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Impact of Farming Systems on the Physical Characteristics of Carcass of Local Breeds Ducks (*Cairina Moschata* Linnæus, 1758) In the South Forest of Côte d'Ivoire

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Abstract

Study was carried out to determine the impact of farming systems on the physical characteristics of carcass of local breed ducks (*Cairina moschata*) 185 days old in the south forest of Côte d'Ivoire. This study involved 20 local breed ducks from two farming systems, with different feeding methods. The animals in the semi-intensive system were fed with a complete feed made from rubber seed residue. The animals in the extensive system searched their own food during raving. At the end of the breeding period, the selected ducks were slaughtered by bleeding, plucked and eviscerated. The live weight recorded to the animals of the semi-intensive system was 1203 g higher than those of the extensive system. Carcass weight and carcass yield were respectively 1538.24 g and 15.86 % higher in the semi-intensive. On the other hand, in terms of offal yield, the animals of the semi-intensive system obtained values 5.2 % lower compared to the animals of the extensive system. Raising ducks in semi-intensive conditions has improved carcass yield and reduced offal yield. In view of these results, the semi-intensive system contributes to improving the productivity of local ducks.

Keywords: Physical characteristics, Carcass, Local breed ducks, Breeding systems, Ivory Coast

INTRODUCTION

In Côte d'Ivoire, the high consumption of animal proteins by the population is inversely proportional to the meat production capacity (Corniaux *et al.*, 2012 ; Kouablebi & Trebi, 2014). The total national production of animal protein supplied by all farm animals covers less than half (46.35 %) of consumption (MIRAH, 2009 ; FAO, 2015). In addition, the production deficit is estimated at 55.4 % for meat and over 87 % for milk and dairy products. This production deficit illustrates the difficulty for the Ivorian state in achieving self-sufficiency in animal proteins. Despite the efforts of governments in the installation and supervision of pastoralists, livestock contributes only 4.5 % to agricultural GDP and 2 % to total GDP in Côte d'Ivoire (MIRAH, 2009). However, among the livestock sectors, poultry farming occupies an important place in meat production. Because, it covers almost half (44 %) of the total national meat production (MIRAH, 2013 ; FAO, 2015). This production includes modern breeding of broilers, laying hens and traditional breeding of local breed poultry such as hens, guinea fowls and ducks. Traditional poultry farming is widely practiced by rural populations. These maintain around 75 % of the national herd with approximately 30,350,000 head in 2012 (MIRAH, 2013). In this practice, the breeding of local ducks is still at a rudimentary stage and knows a very low production (FAO, 2008). Thus, in order to improve the productivity of local breed ducks, these animals were reared in semi-intensive condition where the ducks were fed a complete feed made from rubber seed residue (Amanidja *et al.*, 2019). This study made it possible to obtain heavies ducks in the semi-intensive system compared to the extensive system (Amanidja *et al.*, 2019). However, do these farming systems not influence the physical characteristics of the carcasses produced? This trial will address this concern by undertaking a study of carcass qualities of local breed ducks reared under semi-intensive conditions using stray local breed ducks as controls.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area

The study took place at the Animal Development and Production Learning Center (CAPP) in Bingerville located in the district of Abidjan. With geographical coordinates 5 ° 21'21 "North and 3 ° 53'24" West in degrees, minutes, seconds, Bingerville is located in the dense forest zone of humid tropical climate where the average annual rainfall during the year. The study was 1653 mm with an annual mean temperature of 26.27 ± 1.9 °C and a relative humidity of 81.5 ± 2.40 %.

Animal material

The study involved 20 local breed ducks (*Cairina moschata*) from the semi-intensive farming system and the extensive stray system. The ducks were 185 days old.

Supply Mode

In the semi-intensive system, the ducks were fed with rubber seed residue. In this food, the cake was incorporated respectively at 25 and 30 % (TH 25 and TH 30 %) during the start-up and growth phases. The percentage composition and the nutritional value obtained after bromatological analysis of the feed are shown in Table I. The ducks reared in the extensive system, sought their own food during the straying of the hatching (Ducklings 1 day) up to the stage adult (185 days). These were used as a witness.

Breeding management

In the semi-intensive system, one hundred and fifty (150) ducklings fresh from the hatchery were reared under the conditions described by Amanidja *et al* (2019) until 185 days of age. In the extensive system, ducklings were identified using identification rings before being placed in foster mother ducks. Under the guidance of the adopting mother ducks, the ducklings were left to fend for themselves in their diet. The animals grazed all day and returned in the evening after a long hike in the shelters at night. The subjects used for this study in this system were one hundred (100) ducklings.

Table I : Percentage composition, nutritional and energy value of the 25 % TH and 30 % TH food rations tested in ducklings.

Ingredient	Food rations	
	TH 25 %	TH 30 %
	Start-up	Growth
Maize (%)	43.68	50.00
Wheat middlings (%)	20.00	12.27
Fishmeal (%)	7.50	4.00
Rubber seed (%)	25.00	30.00
Shell (%)	0.70	0.43
Dicalcium phosphate (%)	0.62	1.50
CMV	0.89	0.10
Lysin (%)	0.90	0.90
Methionin (%)	0.41	0.50
Cooking salt (%)	0.30	0.50
Total	100	100
Dry matter (%)	90.20	89.13
Protein (%)	19.00	16.00
Metabolizable energy (kcal/kg)	3009	2800
Calcium (%)	0.84	0.75
Phosphorus (%)	0.45	0.35

TH 25 % : Feed containing 25 % rubber seed residue.

TH 30 % : Feed containing 30 % rubber seed residue.

Slaughter of animals and measurement of parameters

At the end of the growing period (185 days of age), ten ducks were randomly selected from the duck population in each breeding system. In the semi-intensive system ten animals were also randomly selected for the study of carcass characteristics. All subjects were fasted the night before from 4 p.m. to 7 a.m. the next day, then weighed individually before slaughter. The animals were slaughtered by bloodletting, severing the jugular vein located on the left side of the neck. After bleeding, the animals' blood was

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collected in a metal container 10 cm in diameter and 20 cm deep, until the blood stopped flowing. After slaughtering, the animals were reweighed individually before being manually plucked in hot water and reweighed. The animals were immersed in a basin of hot water for 1 to 3 minutes before being plucked. The large tail feathers and wings were plucked first, then the rest of the body feathers.

The harvested feathers were dried in an oven at 80 °C for 24 hours before being weighed. They were then eviscerated and cut according to ACIA (2003) prescriptions. The kidneys embedded in the lumbosacral bones were removed by severing the ureters, after having released the ovarian cluster and extracted the oviduct in the female or the testes in the male. Offal (heart, liver, gizzard, head and legs) and non-consumable parts (feathers, blood, intestine, kidneys and lungs) were taken and weighed using an electronic scale. The carcass including the neck was also weighed. The main returns were expressed using the formulas below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{yield after slaughter (\%)} &= P2 / P1 \times 100 \\ \text{yield after evisceration (\%)} &= P3 / P1 \times 100 \\ \text{Carcass yield (\%)} &= P4 / P1 \times 100 \\ \text{yield of carcass components (\%)} &= P5 / P1 \times 100 \\ \text{yield of offal or non-edible parts (\%)} &= P6 / P1 \times 100 \\ \text{yield after slaughter (\%)} &= P2 / P1 \times 100 \\ \text{yield after evisceration (\%)} &= P3 / P1 \times 100 \\ \text{Carcass yield (\%)} &= P4 / P1 \times 100 \\ \text{yield of carcass components (\%)} &= P5 / P1 \times 100 \\ \text{yield of offal or non-edible parts (\%)} &= P6 / P1 \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

P1: Live weight of animals

P2: Weight after slaughter and plucking

P3: Weight after evisceration

P4: Carcass weight

P5: Weight of different part of the body

P6: Weight of the offal or the non-consumable part

Statistical analysis

A one-way inter system analysis of variance (ANOVA 1) using the statistical processing software "STATISTICA" version 7.1 was applied to the various parameters. In the event of a significant difference, the classification of the means was obtained by the Mann-Whitney U test at the 5 % threshold.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Carcass weight and yields

The different values of weight and carcass yield obtained are listed in Table II. The average live weights of ducks driven in semi-intensive conditions were higher than those of animals driven in the extensive system. A significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed between the live weights of ducks in the rearing systems. After slaughter and evisceration, the carcass weight of the ducks from the semi-intensive system was higher compared to the ducks from the extensive system with also significant differences ($p < 0.05$). Carcass yields in semi-intensive system animals were higher compared to extensive system ducks with significant differences ($p < 0.05$). However, the best performance was obtained with ducks fed the diet containing rubber meal.

Table II : Weight and yields of ducks according to the farming system

Farming system Parameters	Extensif Wandering	Semi-intensif Experimental	P > F
Live weight (g)	2735 ± 57 ^a	3938 ± 52 ^c	0.01
Weight after slaughter (g)	2619.67 ± 0.85 ^a	3809.62 ± 0.35 ^c	0.02
Weight after evisceration (g)	2198.94 ± 0.27 ^a	3628.27 ± 0.71 ^c	0.01
Carcass weight (g)	2077.23 ± 0.39 ^a	3615.47 ± 0.28 ^c	0.01

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Yield after slaughter (%)	95.78 ± 0.92 ^a	96.74 ± 1.20 ^a	0.91
Yield after evisceration (%)	80.40 ± 0.85 ^a	92.13 ± 1.52 ^c	0.01
Carcass yield (%)	75.95 ± 0.96 ^a	91.81 ± 1.48 ^c	0.03

The mean superscript values of the same letters on the same row are not statistically different ($p > 0.05$).

Carcass composition

The weight and the proportions relative to the live weight of the different components of the carcass are presented in Table III. In ducks of the extensive system, the weight of the thighs was 243.63 ± 0.73 g against 413.50 ± 0.27 g for the experimental subjects. The corresponding proportions were 8.80 % and 10.50 % respectively. Statistical analysis indicates that the average weight of the legs of ducks in the semi-intensive system was greater than that of stray animals at the 5 % threshold. This same superiority was observed with the average whole back weight which was 354.42 ± 0.92 g under improved conditions and 266.66 ± 0.87 g in the stray system. The mean weights of the thighs, wings, full dorsum, breast and neck in subjects of the semi-intensive system were higher than those of the extensive system with significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between its components in the breeding systems.

Table III : Weight and yield of ducks in relation to the live weight of the components of the carcass depending on the farming system.

Farming system Parameters	Extensif Wandering	Semi-intensif Experimental	P > F
Thigh (g)	243.68 ± 0.73 ^a	413.50 ± 0.27 ^b	0.01
Wings (g)	298.93 ± 0.90 ^a	357.17 ± 0.55 ^b	0.03
Full dorsum (g)	266.66 ± 0.87 ^a	354.42 ± 0.92 ^b	0.02
Breast (g)	307.14 ± 0.31 ^a	581.64 ± 0.80 ^b	0.01
Neck (g)	159.17 ± 0.75 ^a	197.30 ± 0.99 ^b	0.02
Thigh yield (%)	8.80 ± 0.53 ^a	10.50 ± 0.81 ^a	0.68
Wing yield (%)	10.93 ± 0.65 ^a	9.07 ± 0.47 ^a	0.66
Full dorsum yield (%)	9.75 ± 0.85 ^a	9.15 ± 0.65 ^a	0.74
Breast yield (%)	11.23 ± 0.51 ^a	14.77 ± 0.18 ^a	0.52
Neck yield (%)	5.82 ± 0.25 ^a	5.01 ± 0.76 ^a	0.81

The mean superscript values of the same letters on the same row are not statistically different ($p > 0.05$).

Offal

The weight and the proportions in relation to the live weight of the various components of the offal are recorded in Table IV. The offal weights of subjects in the semi-intensive system were markedly greater than those of ducks in the extensive system. The mean head weight in males (102.00 ± 0.97 g) was lower compared to that of ducks (117.3 ± 0.65 g) in the semi-intensive medium. Significant differences were observed ($p < 0.05$) between head weights in animals of the semi-intensive system and those of the extensive system. The average leg weight of ducks in the extensive system (89.56 ± 0.43 g) was higher than that of animals (77.23 ± 0.85 g) in the improved system. A significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed between the paw weights. Regarding the mean heart weights, a significant superiority ($p < 0.05$) was observed in the wandering subjects (35.00 ± 1.88 g) compared to the experimental subjects (26.02 ± 1.42 g). The mean weight of the liver was 69.15 ± 1.00 g in the stray animals against 58.00 ± 1.55 g in improved medium. A significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed between the mean liver weights in animals of the semi-intensive system and those of the extensive system. A significant difference was also observed. Observed at the level of the mean weights of the gizzard which were respectively 85.63 ± 0.83 g for the animals of the stray environment against 65.84 ± 0.71 g in the experimental subjects. The offal yield from animals in the extensive stray system was superior to that of the subjects in the experimental environment with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between offal from animals in the semi-intensive system and those in the extensive system.

Table IV : Weight and yield of duck offal in relation to live weight depending on the farming system

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Farming system Parameters	Extensif Wandering	Semi-intensif Experimental	P>F
Heart (g)	35 ± 8 ^a	26.02 ± 0.42 ^b	0.03
Liver (g)	69.15 ± 0.95 ^a	58 ± 6 ^b	0.01
Gizzard (g)	85.63 ± 0.83 ^a	65.84 ± 0.71 ^b	0.04
Head (g)	102 ± 7 ^a	117.3 ± 0.65 ^b	0.01
Leg (g)	89.56 ± 0.43 ^a	77.23 ± 0.85 ^b	0.00
Heart yield (%)	1.28 ± 0.89 ^a	0.66 ± 1.42 ^b	0.04
Liver yield (%)	2.53 ± 1.91 ^a	1.47 ± 0.55 ^a	0.86
Gizzard yield (%)	3.13 ± 0.75 ^a	1.67 ± 1.07 ^b	0.03
Head yield (%)	3.72 ± 0.98 ^a	2.97 ± 0.11 ^b	0.86
Foot yield (%)	3.27 ± 0.33 ^a	1.96 ± 0.57 ^c	0.01

The mean superscript values of the same letters on the same row are not statistically different ($p > 0.05$).

Non-consumable parts

The weight and the proportions in relation to the live weight of the different components of the non-consumable parts are recorded in Table V. In ducks in semi-intensive environments, the average weight of the feathers was lower compared to animals in the stray system. However, no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed between feather weights. The mean blood weight was higher in experimental subjects compared to stray subjects. There is a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) according to statistical tests between the mean blood weights. In the stray system, the average kidney weights were lower to that of animals in the semi-intensive system. The mean weight of the kidneys obtained was 3.84 ± 0.96 g in the stray medium and 5.93 ± 0.14 g for the experimental subjects in the semi-intensive medium. In the lungs, the mean weight of the wandering ducks was higher than that of the animals of the improved environment, with 37.20 ± 1.49 g for the wandering subjects against 21.93 ± 1.71 g for the experimental subjects ($p < 0.05$).

Table V : Weight and proportions of the non-consumable parts of the ducks compared to the live weight according to the farming system

Farming system Parameters	Extensif Wandering	Semi-intensif Experimental	P>F
Feathers (g)	91,35 ± 0,52 ^a	89,58 ± 0,76 ^a	0,53
Blood (g)	136,20 ± 0,35 ^a	169,37 ± 0,95 ^c	0,04
Kidneys (g)	3,84 ± 0,9 ^a	6,93 ± 0,44 ^b	0,01
Lungs (g)	37,20 ± 0,24 ^a	18,95 ± 0,71 ^b	0,02
Intestine (g)	200,40 ± 0,78 ^a	194,90 ± 0,88 ^b	0,01
Feather yield (%)	3,34 ± 0,54 ^a	2,27 ± 0,27 ^b	0,00
Blood yield (%)	4,98 ± 0,32 ^a	4,30 ± 0,62 ^a	0,73
Kidney yield (%)	0,14 ± 0,99 ^a	0,17 ± 1,12 ^c	0,03
Lungs yield (%)	1,36 ± 0,10 ^a	0,50 ± 0,16 ^b	0,01
Intestine yield (%)	7,32 ± 0,21 ^a	4,94 ± 0,06 ^b	0,04

The mean superscript values of the same letters on the same row are not statistically different ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

The weight and carcass yield of local breed ducks in the semi-intensive system was higher than that of ducks in the extensive system. This difference in carcass yield could be explained by the fact that the ducks in the semi-intensive system gained more muscle from the feed. The results were similar to those carried out on local breed ducks in Turkey and Nigeria respectively by Isguzar *et al.* (2002) and Etuk & Abasiokong (2006). Also, studies by Deka & Kalita (2004), on broilers reared in semi-intensive conditions, found that animals which were heavier, had a higher carcass yield. The offal weights (heart, liver, gizzard, head, leg) of ducks reared in the extensive system recorded the highest values compared to the ducks of the semi-intensive system. This variation in offal weight between the two systems is linked to straying marked by

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strong muscle activity. Thus, during straying the need for oxygen for the heart, lung and skeletal muscles increased in proportion with the evolution of their metabolic performance, which led to an enlarged heart and lungs. To this end, Rolfe & Brand (1997) reported that a lot of movement or intense physical activity leads to enlarged heart and lungs. The gizzard weight increased in ducks of the extensive system due to the diet to which these animals are subjected. Indeed, animals during straying consume all kinds of food. Consumed foods such as whole seeds, gravel and shoots of different plants could cause the gizzard to exert additional pressures to crush these consumed foods (Roy *et al.*, 2003 ; Deka & Kalita, 2004).

The leg weight of ducks in the extensive system was greater than that of ducks in the semi-intensive system. This difference could be attributed to the wandering practiced by these animals in order to cover their nutritional needs. In general, the ducks in the semi-intensive system recorded the lowest offal yields. Our results were in agreement with those obtained in the local chickens of Mizoram and on ducklings fed with a ration based on cashew apple respectively by Sharma (1995) and Aboh *et al.* (2011).

These authors recorded lower offal yields in the semi-intensive system. As for the weights of the non-consumable parts (feathers, blood, kidneys and lungs), the weight of the lungs of ducks in the extensive system was greater than that of ducks in the semi-intensive system. This difference in lung weights could be explained by the high intensity physical activity of these animals during straying. Thus, during straying the oxygen demand of the air sacs increased, they filled with air in order to allow the metabolic reactions of the body to continue, resulting in an enlarged lung (Tona, 2007).

The results were similar to those of Isguzar *et al.* (2002) ; Omojola *et al.* (2007) carried out in Turkey and Nigeria respectively on local breed ducks. In contrast, the blood and kidney weights of ducks in the extensive system were lower compared to ducks in the semi-intensive system. This variation in blood and kidney weights would be linked to the undernourishment of the ducks in the extensive system and to the medical treatments carried out on the animals during the experiment in the semi-intensive system.

Indeed, according to Kouadio *et al.* (2010) straying in the intensive system covered less of the poultry maintenance needs. This diet may lead to a slowdown in metabolic reactions which can lead to anemia (Rolfe & Brand, 1997). As for kidney weights, the use of anticoccidial drugs and antibiotics during the rearing periods are thought to be the cause of the increase in the weight of the kidneys of the subjects in the semi-intensive system. The results were in agreement with those of the work carried out in broilers in Dakar and in ducklings in Benin respectively by Ibrahim (2001) and Aboh *et al.* (2011). The percentage of feathers obtained with ducks in the semi-intensive system was lower compared to that of ducks in the extensive system. The results of this study would agree with those of Mérat *et al.* (1980) and Fotsa (2008) who reported that the heaviest birds would always have a lower percentage of feathers.

CONCLUSION

It emerges from this study that the live weight of animals in a semi-intensive environment is greater than that of subjects in an extensive environment wandering. The semi-intensive system allowed greater meat production and better carcass yield. The offal components have less weight with the semi-intensive farming system favoring a lower offal yield.

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